

Appendix C: Orbit maps of a Helmi Streams' subclump star

We randomly picked a subclump star and integrated its orbit for 20 Gyr in the fiducial potential with a triaxial NFW halo for a range of $0.95 < p < 1.05$ and $1.10 < q < 1.30$ to create orbit maps. Figure C.1 shows the map in (R, z) , Fig. C.2 shows the map in (x, y) , Fig. C.3 shows the map in (x, z) and Fig. C.4 shows the map in (y, z) . By inspecting these maps, different orbit families can be recognised. The resonantly trapping $\Omega_\phi : \Omega_z$ is 1:1 resonance clearly stands out for $p > 1$ in Fig. C.4, while such a region is not apparent for $p < 1$. The y -tubes and z -tubes can be recognised easily from Fig. C.3 and Fig. C.4, as on these families the star orbits rotate around the y and z axis, respectively.

Fig. C.1. Orbit in Galactocentric cylindrical (R, z) of a Helmi Streams' subclump star in Galactic potentials with a triaxial NFW halo for a range of p and q . Orbits in axisymmetric potentials are indicated in dark blue.

Fig. C.2. Orbit in Galactocentric Cartesian (x, y) of a Helmi Streams' subclump star in Galactic potentials with a triaxial NFW halo for a range of p and q . Orbits in axisymmetric potentials are indicated in dark blue.

Fig. C.3. Orbit in Galactocentric Cartesian (x, z) of a Helmi Streams' subclump star in Galactic potentials with a triaxial NFW halo for a range of p and q . Orbits in axisymmetric potentials are indicated in dark blue.

Fig. C.4. Orbit in Galactocentric Cartesian (y, z) of a Helmi Streams' subclump star in Galactic potentials with a triaxial NFW halo for a range of p and q . Orbits in axisymmetric potentials are indicated in dark blue. The $\Omega_\phi : \Omega_z$ is 1:1 resonance stands out clearly, as the orbit becomes planar.

Appendix D: Orbital frequencies of the Helmi Streams

Figure D.1 shows the distribution of orbital frequencies of the Helmi Streams stars in the potential where we have replaced the DM halo with a triaxial halo for a range of p and q . If stars are on the $\Omega_\phi : \Omega_z$ resonance, they fall on the dotted line in the figure. Using ΔL_y and ΔL_z to classify the orbits, we checked and found that the orbital frequencies of z tube orbits and truly resonant orbit are determined reliably. However, the algorithm sometimes has some problems to determine the orbital frequencies of y tube orbits, which are either classified as resonant orbits or placed on a wrong branch, which both stand out as line features in Fig. D.1. This can be attributed to the fact that the cylindrical coordinates (R, ϕ, z) are not the most suitable coordinates to describe the motion of y tube orbits. However, the frequency determination is good enough for our purposes, which is to use the median of the orbital frequencies of the hiL, loL and subclump stars to map out where orbital resonances reside (see Fig. 4 of the main text). It is also interesting to see the effect of the $\Omega_\phi : \Omega_z$ 1:1 resonance for $p > 1$, clearly trapping orbits, and $p < 1$, resulting in a chaotic and thus underpopulated region in frequency space.

Fig. D.1. Orbital frequency distribution of the Helmi Streams’ stars in Galactic potentials with a triaxial NFW halo for a range of p and q . Axisymmetric potentials ($p = 1$) are indicated with a blue-grey facecolor. The hiL stars are encircled in red, the loL stars in blue and the subclump stars in black. The dotted line indicates the $\Omega_\phi : \Omega_z$ 1:1 resonance, which acts as a separatrix in potentials with $p < 1$ and resonantly traps orbits for $p > 1$.